

The Role Of Social Media In The Most Prominent Fields Of Life And Its Problems

دور الإعلام الاجتماعي في أبرز الميادين الحياتية وإشكالياته

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Abstract

The study concluded that social media in particular has taken a large and important space in the most prominent fields of contemporary life, especially open-source social media, and as long as most aspects of human, natural and cosmic activity; It was worth studying all their aspects to clarify the position of Sharia and the law on them and their rulings on them. There is no doubt about the necessity and necessity of submitting them to their controls to ensure optimal benefit from them, as they are among the services that are indispensable in our contemporary time. Accordingly, this study dealt with the issue of social media through the following images: Social media in the most prominent areas of life and its problems. Topics related to the media today are among the topics worthy of study and care, as the media occupies a large and influential space in various fields of life. Perhaps social media is one of the most prominent types of media in terms of influence and importance, as it is based on transmitting news and information from the community to the community itself, to achieve one of the purposes of news, guidance or guidance through its various means such as clubs, forums, places of worship, social networks, newspapers and books. The media directed to a particular place, group, or segment of society is considered its social media, such as the media directed to the community of a particular city or a segment such as women, or a group such as the disabled. Whereas social media is of such vitality and importance; This topic has been allocated according to the requirements of the study. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: social media images, the most prominent fields of life, the problem.

ملخص البحث

قد توصلت الدراسة إلى أن الإعلام الاجتماعي خصوصًا قد أخذ حيزًا كبيرًا ومهمًا في أبرز ميادين الحياة المعاصرة خصوصًا الإعلام الاجتماعي المفتوح المصادر، وطالما معظم جوانب النشاط الإنساني والطبيعي والكوني؛ فكان جديرًا أن تدرس كل جوانبها لبيان موقف الشريعة والقانون منهما وأحكامهما فيهما؛ ولا جدال في وجوب وضروعة خضوعهما لضوابطهما لضمان استفادة مثلى منهما باعتبارهما من الخدمات التي لا غنى عنها في زمننا المعاصر. بناء على ذلك تناولت هذه الدراسة موضوع الإعلام الاجتماعي من خلال الصور الآتية:

الإعلام الاجتماعي في أبرز الميادين الحياتية وإشكالياته.

وتعد الموضوعات المتعلقة بالإعلام في وقتنا الحاضر من الموضوعات الجديرة بالدراسة والعناية، حيث يشغل الإعلام حيزًا كبيرًا ومؤثرًا في مختلف ميادين الحياة. ولعل الإعلام الاجتماعي هو أحد أبرز أنواع الإعلام من جهة التأثير والأهمية، حيث يركز على نقل الأخبار والمعلومات من المجتمع إلى المجتمع نفسه، لتحقيق غرض من الأغراض الإخبارية أو التوجيهية أو الإرشادية عبر وسائله المتنوعة كالنوادي والملتقيات ودور العبادة وشبكات التواصل الاجتماعي والصحف والكتب. ويعتبر الإعلام الموجّه إلى مكان أو فئة أو شريحة معينة من شرائح المجتمع هو إعلامها الاجتماعي، كإعلام الموجه لمجتمع مدينة معينة أو شريحة كالنساء، أو فئة كالمعاقين. ولما كان الإعلام الاجتماعي بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعًا لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: صور الإعلام الاجتماعي، أبرز الميادين الحياتية، الإشكالية.

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We will try, God willing, in this topic to shed light on the roles played by social media in the most prominent fields of life, and review some relevant models, and extract the most prominent problems that may face or stand in the way of communicating its contents and messages.

The first requirement: the role of social media towards social issues

There are many social issues and problems floating on the surface of life, and many are the means that mark and monitor them, and social media aims or is supposed to aim in general for direction and influence. It is obvious that he has an active role towards these issues, and the extent of the power, influence, vitality and ability of the media to direct individuals and societies has already been clarified.

Social media is considered one of the effective social media in this field, as it is possible to monitor many issues and problems, whether at the social level or otherwise. These sites occupied a large and influential space among various other means, although this does not absolve them of responsibility for the spread of some negative phenomena, such as the spread of hate speech in many societies, which contributed significantly to the spread of this phenomenon; This prompted some parties to rush to address this phenomenon and reduce it, such as what was done during the (Hate Speech in Digital and Social Media Conference). Among the most prominent conclusions and recommendations that emerged from this conference are the following:

1. The presence of social networking sites in the media scene has greatly contributed to the spread and spread of hate speech, increased the complexity of this phenomenon and deepened its dangers on the ground.
2. One of the sources of hate speech is the frantic race and unethical competition between professional social media on the one hand and non-professional social media on the other.
3. Emphasis on the need to address this phenomenon through several mechanisms, including: introducing media education into educational systems, establishing observatories to monitor and monitor hate speech in all social media, and enacting laws that would reduce the risks and consequences of this phenomenon.

On the other hand, social media may contribute positively, constructively and influential in some cases, as in the issue of religiosity, for example, which is one of the important issues of interest to many human societies, as most societies seek through their social media to spread and consolidate the principles of their religion among their circles and forums, These means are one of the focal points in this missionary aspect.

In Muslim societies - for example - social media plays a major role in spreading religiosity among their circles through its various means, whether through personal media, such as family, friends, mosque and educational institutions, or through mass media, such as television, radio and publishing houses, where these means play a positive role. Towards the community by guiding, educating and educating its members and calling them to a correct understanding of the religion of Islam and its teachings.

The family - for example - is the first incubator for man, and from it the general concept of religion and religiosity is formed, whether directly through directives and instructions, or indirectly through observed behaviors and practices.

Perhaps it is no secret to anyone that these means are a double-edged sword. They may be one of the biggest factors in increasing faith and obtaining a correct understanding of religiosity. At that time, the individual and society will increase adherence and pride in his religion. Which will result in weak faith in souls and hearts, and presumptuousness against God's prohibitions, and the drift of many societies towards corruption and moral decay is only due to the wrong understanding of religion and the wrong practice of religiosity to which social media have contributed greatly. The various means together to publish it correctly, because all that is published in these means of materials greatly affects the members of society, as they are the ones who make their minds and ideas.

The summary of what it aspires to explain in this regard is that social media has an active role in social issues, not only in monitoring social phenomena and issues; Rather, it goes beyond searching for its causes, developing appropriate solutions for it, and perhaps addressing it -sometimes- through support, guidance, education and awareness, creating free spaces for expression, and securing protection and care for influencers in social media who carry lofty messages and content providers that are purposeful and incited to adhere to human and ethical values. .

The second requirement: the role of social media in the most prominent fields of life

First - The role of social media in the field of education:

1 .Concept of Education:

Where the concept of education is defined as: "what the mature generations teach to the generations that have not yet matured to face life." Therefore, the concept of education includes all the information, experiences, behaviors and cultures provided by the parties participating in this process to generations that have not yet matured.

2 .The role of social media in the field of education:

There is no doubt that social media is an important educational resource in many societies, and there is no doubt that this rapid technical development has made these means a powerfully influential factor in that field, and since television combined movement, image and sound, its impact was greater than most of the means. In addition to its spread in many societies, and perhaps we will clarify through the following models the extent of the impact of social media in this field. In a study conducted on a group of parents to measure the impact of (MBC3) on children, the percentage of children who watched the channel was 81.66%, and 90% of them watch that channel freely, and in measuring the extent to which children are affected by what is shown on that channel; 44.99% answered yes, and in measuring the child's imitation of the displayed scenes, the proportions were as follows The following: 18.33% always imitate, 56.77% imitate sometimes, 24.99% do not imitate. As for the viewership rate, the study found that 70% of children watch the channel for more than an hour.

In the light of this study and through this brief presentation of the results of the study of one of the dozens of channels directed to children, it was possible to observe the extent to which children are attached to these means, which will lead in one way or another to be affected by their contents according to the results of this study. Parents tend to leave their children in front of these screens without supervision or inspection of what is issued by them, which is another problem that is added to the long list of problems that our societies suffer from at the educational level due to the seriousness and sensitivity of that stage and its direct impact on the personality of the individual, and its contribution greatly to the formation of His moral and behavioral system, as the child at this stage is similar to the fertile land in which everything that is sown grows.

Among the important studies in this context are; A study conducted by the world of communication (Halloran), the results of which indicated that 97% of children under the age of eleven who were included in the study strongly trust television as a media source more than they trust any other source from, and when asked: If you heard a story from your parents or manager, or who radio or television; Which narration do you believe? 54% of these respondents answered that they believe television more than any other source.

It is worth mentioning here that not everything that is read, heard or seen in these channels is pure entertainment. Rather, each carries with it a lot of meanings, contents, directions and values to be promoted to show its impact on the recipient in the long run.

The entertainment and artistic materials - for example - provided by these media outlets, such as films, programs, songs, series - Arab and Western - and animation, directly affect the lifestyles of many members of society, especially children and adolescents, who are supposed to be the mainstay and foundation of the future; Rather, it may have opened their minds to corrupt values, ideas and cultures that they may try to emulate in their daily lives.

On this; The role of social media is no less valuable and important than the role of the educational institution in the social upbringing of the individual, along with the family institution, because the time a child or young person spends in dealing with the media is no less important than the time he spends in school, and therefore it is necessary to pay attention The elements of social media for the child from an Islamic perspective, which are as follows:

- a. The goal is to build the integrated personality of the child by simplifying Islamic concepts and paying attention to the ways of displaying them.
- B. To be keen on instilling the concepts of good and evil and explaining their effects. It is also worth paying attention to Islamic personalities and the lives of the prophets and the righteous, and addressing unseen issues without neglect or preoccupation.
- c. Gradual handling of concepts and knowledge, addressing emotion and respecting reason; It is preferable that this be done using the classical Arabic language, provided that Islam is a complete reference in all these works.

As for the educational level; Social media faces many difficulties, foremost of which is the scarcity of available capabilities, and one of the results of this is the lack of effectiveness of these means; Which led to the disruption of one of the most important mechanisms for the dissemination of knowledge in the masses, as it is certain that scientific culture is one of the most important building blocks in building society, and with the acceleration of scientific and technical developments in the last quarter of the last century and the beginning of this century; The importance of education and knowledge as one of the basic components of economic and social growth has increased.

The development of social media has made it an influential force on our intellectual and cultural life. What posed a major challenge to the educational institution and its values; A child from an early age is surrounded by many means, which will affect him sooner or later.

The most prominent problems in this field are the weak coordination and cooperation between the relevant parties. Whether it is in the consolidation of social values, or in the delivery of information that increases the capabilities and awareness of the individual and develops his skills. As the social media is supposed to constitute an important tributary of education and education alike. Due to its wide spread, power of influence, and abundance of materials, it is

unfortunate that the matter may not stop at the often poor coordination between the relevant parties; It may even reach the stage of conflict and competition in the values between them.

The way out of this problem lies in deepening the link of cooperation between social media, school and home to consolidate information or values, ideals and trends, and work to develop the student's mind to be able to distinguish the contents of these means, and work to prepare carefully studied plans and strategies to confront the problems related to the relevant parties.

The impact of these means must also be exploited and employed in them to benefit the educational process; The activation of these means in the educational environment has a great and undeniable impact; Towards using the theater to show purposeful plays or cinema to show school films that "deal with topics related to the school curricula, some of which deal with, for example: the structure of the atom, the structure of the human body..." and other means; Such as the Internet, and other means that can be benefited from in this field.

Some research and studies have revealed that students learn in different ways, some of them learn by reading, and others learn by listening, and most of them are through reading and listening, and there is no doubt that reading needs books and other visual aids, and the development of the listening skill needs audio media, and based on that we can say Social media can revolutionize this field if used properly.

Second- The role of social media in the political field:

Before proceeding to talk about the role of social media in the political field;

First of all, it is good for us to refer to the concept of politics.

1. The concept of politics, linguistically and idiomatically:

a. Politics Linguistically: Doing something with what is right for it. It is said: They have caused them to suffer from a bug, and the basis of the matter is a policy that he has done.

B. Politics idiomatically: is the art of governing human societies.

Here the definition includes the rule of states and the rule of other human societies, and the word governance here means: the organized authority and the institutions of leadership.

2. The role of social media in the political field:

Social media plays an important and influential role in the field of politics, which is to direct the masses towards a certain behavior or direction. As if it is ideological, ideological, partisan, or towards an individual or collective leadership, where it tries to influence and guide the masses by exploiting its various and possible means.

Social media also contributes significantly to the process of political upbringing among members of society through the dissemination of news and information, coverage of political events, and enlightening society in all its segments of what is new in this field. Which in turn contributes to raising the level of political awareness among its members.

Through the following model, it is possible to review the active role of one of the social media in this field:

Social networking sites have brought about great transformations at the social level in general, and at the political level in particular, especially in what is known as the events of the Arab Spring, which are the popular revolutions that erupted since early (2011 AD) and are still continuing until this year (2021 AD) in some Arab countries. The social media, through its various sites, participated in a major and active role in it.

Where these sites contributed significantly to increasing popular pressure on the political systems in those countries; Which eventually led to the fall of most of them, and the principle of those protests at the time was in Tunisia a few weeks before the end of the year (2010 AD), then spread to Egypt, Yemen, Libya and Syria in the year (2011 AD), and the demonstrators used social networking sites for interaction and communication with each other and expression. About their opinions and aspirations and the organization of their movement, as these sites were used to cover many events in that period. In addition to the above; These sites have contributed to removing the barrier of fear and dread from the souls of political and social activists, considering that "if the matter is clear," it also helped create more interaction and solidarity among other peoples who are going through the same political, social and economic conditions and the same general conditions.

From this model, we move to talk about one of the main axes in the political field, which is public opinion and the role of social media in crystallizing it, shaping it and pushing it to be effective and influential.

Third - The role of social media in shaping public opinion:

1. The concept of public opinion, linguistically and idiomatically:

a. Linguistically, opinion has several meanings, including: "reason, belief, planning, consideration, and contemplation.

B. General language: comprehensive.

c. Idiomatically speaking, public opinion: "It is a general social orientation, or a common impression that organizes a certain group of people around a specific issue in a specific time and place, accepting, rejecting, or neutralizing, with what this requires from a subconscious emotional orientation, and realistic apparent and tangible behavior".

.2 The role of social media in shaping public opinion:

Public opinion is considered one of the dangerous and sensitive topics of social sciences, politics, and the media. In free societies, it illuminates the rulers, officials and other individuals and groups the way to the nation's advancement and political, economic and social progress. With this public awareness, and with this frank opinion, the nation takes the right path. There is no cheating, bribery, or shortcoming. There is no injustice, persecution, or falsehood in the election, because public opinion in free nations is alert and alert to every small and large, due to several factors, causes and mechanisms that guarantee it control and control over its reality and future.

In contrast to the enslaved nations in which public opinion is captive, monopolized, and straitened, so that in the societies of these nations there is room for every deceiver, the corrupt, the unjust and the corrupt, morals are dissolved, development projects, modernization programs and reforms are hidden, determination weakens, and despair and flight prevail. Public opinion in these nations has no weight or consideration.

If these data are decided and analysts, researchers and scholars agree on them, social media has a major role in shaping public opinion regarding an issue, whether it is political, social, economic, etc., where its function lies and its role is manifested in mobilizing the masses to confront certain issues or events, by telling Community members deal with these issues through its various means such as newspapers, magazines, meetings, bulletins, and any other means deemed necessary or appropriate by those in charge of social media to guide the masses and influence their opinions and behaviour. Thus, social media contributes to shaping public opinion, whether at the local or international level.

However, this directive, according to the foregoing, may be towards the development and renaissance of the society, so that the public opinion becomes a guide and guides the government and the authority in identifying the needs, aspirations and goals of the society, or it may be marginalized and left without consideration to exacerbate crises and reach the point of collapse and explosion.

Social media is one of the most important factors affecting the formation of this public opinion, and through the following model, the role of one of these media can be reviewed:

Where the mosque is one of the prominent means, in some societies, in the formation of public opinion; The mosque is not only a place of worship; Rather, it is a guiding, awareness-raising and educational institution, in which members of society meet five times to listen to one book - the Noble Qur'an - and receive the same instructions from it. In this place, they feel the bonds of brotherhood and solidarity that unite them while they are in flat rows behind one imam.

The mosque is also an important cultural reference for all issues of Islamic society, because its members receive one culture, meet in one place, and many discussions take place between them on various societal issues, which contributes greatly to unifying opinions and collect them on the road either.

Fourth - The role of social media in the security field:

1 .The concept of security, linguistically and idiomatically

a. Security is a language: a sense of peace and reassurance, and it is against fear.

B. Security idiomatically: the tranquility that negates the fear and dread of the human being, individually or as a group, in all aspects of life.

2 .The role of social media in the security field:

The importance of this type of media is evident in light of the conflicts and challenges experienced by Arab and Islamic societies, especially during the recent years, as this period was characterized by the media struggle, which was provided with all the capabilities and means by which those with influence in rogue regimes and those with destructive principles and deviant ideas work.

And since the security field is one of the fields concerned with community service; Social media had a prominent role in it, as there is no doubt that this field is one of the main axes for the stability of any society, and accordingly, the current research will, in the following lines, clarify the role of social media in this field.

Social media plays a major role in the security field, especially by highlighting the efforts and sacrifices of the groups concerned with providing and working on it. Publishing the news of this segment, discussing its problems, and explaining its role in community service. It also works to guide and educate the public about crimes, misdemeanors and penalties, and urge them to maintain proper behavior, and to abide by everything that ensures the protection and stability of society.

In this regard, it is necessary to briefly mention the role of the mosque in this field as well, as it contributes significantly through sermons, lessons and lectures to educating its pilgrims about the importance of community security, and ways to preserve it, and warning them against everything that could destabilize the security and stability of society. Such as crimes and misguided and destructive ideas, and urging cooperation with the employees of the security system and helping them to perform their tasks.

Perhaps one of the most important goals that social media seeks to achieve in this field are:

1. Creating a feeling in the individual that there is an authority derived from the will of society capable of protecting him.
2. Consolidating the belief that this party is always ready to provide it with its knowledge in everything related to the safety and security of society, and that it is able to overcome all difficulties that threaten its interests and stability.
3. Demonstrate seriousness in pursuing those who tamper with the laws and those who disregard the generally accepted and neglected systems, so that they do not continue to deviate, thus endangering the interests of society and its members.

The third requirement: the problems of social media

The most prominent problems facing social media, which may prevent it from performing its functions, performing its role and achieving its goals, are as follows:

1. Contrast between endoscopy and application; For example, we often hear in many social media the necessity and importance of striving to solve the issues and problems of society, while the reality contradicts this claim to a large extent, through exaggerated attention to the entertainment aspect at the expense of the most important and influential aspects, which Ultimately, it reduces the positive effectiveness of social media on society.
2. The absence or weakness of coordination between the relevant authorities. Every institution, agency, or ministry concerned with societal affairs has its own vision and directions, which in turn is reflected negatively and negligently on the community, and this may be noticed through the prevalence of some conflicting or contradictory behaviors or ideas among some of its members. Accordingly, there must be complementarity in coordination between these parties to enable social media to play its role in building and reforming society.
3. The marginalization of some means and the regression of some of them on the level of positive influence in Islamic societies. Cinema and theater, for example, were not used in an optimal way despite their great impact in many cases in building personality and shaping awareness; The vast gap in the exploitation of these means can be observed by comparing the use of these tools in Western societies or in former socialist societies, and the use of these means to benefit from them at all levels in Islamic societies.
4. Limited material and moral support for social media compared to some other areas that are less productive or effective in terms of positive impact on community members.
5. Absence of departments or bodies concerned with dealing with social media issues and facing its challenges and developments, in addition to the shortcomings of legislation and regulatory laws.
6. Difficulty in controlling and censoring the content and content of social media; Especially in light of the changing and accelerating technical and informational development.
7. The absence of clear visions and goals among many concerned with social aspects, whether at the official level represented by government agencies or civil society institutions.
8. Lack of awareness among many individuals and organizations of the importance of social media and its impact on their lives and activities in particular, and on society in general.

Conclusion

The current study reached a number of results, which are:

1. Definitions of the concept of social media fluctuate between limiting it to the generality of what electronic social media offers,
2. Dissemination of what is issued by the media in a society.
3. There are many legal controls and provisions that should be observed and adhered to in the means, messages and topics of social media by including them in binding legal articles regulating media work.
4. The most prominent problems of social media are the weak coordination and cooperation between the relevant parties.
5. Lack of awareness among members of societies of its importance and its impact on their lives, in addition to the difficulty of controlling and controlling its contents and contents.

Margins:

It is every talk that provokes feelings of hatred towards a component of m One or more of the components of society, and implicitly calls for the exclusion of its members by expulsion, annihilation, or the curtailment of rights, Zulekha Abu Risha, Hate Speech, Al-Ghad newspaper, Amman, June 20, 2016

()Jordan Media Institute (2016) Conference on Hate Speech in Digital and Social Media, held in Amman, on April 26-27 imi.edu.jo/ar/details/4375 Final statement.

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